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**DER PATIENT IM DATENNETZ –
CHANCEN UND RISIKEN
COMPUTERBASIERTER
PATIENTENDOSSIERE**

Kurzfassung der Studie
“Computerbasierte Patientendossiers – Chancen und Risiken”

**LES PATIENTS SUR RÉSEAU –
AVANTAGES ET RISQUES
DES DOSSIERS INFORMATISÉS DE
PATIENTS**

Résumé de l'étude
“Computerbasierte Patientendossiers – Chancen und Risiken”

**THE PATIENT IN THE DATA NETWORK –
ADVANTAGES AND RISKS
OF COMPUTER-BASED PATIENT
RECORDS**

Short version of the TA-study
“Computerbasierte Patientendossiers – Chancen und Risiken”

Editorial in german and french only.

Diese Reihe der TA-Publikationen enthält die Ergebnisse der Studien, die im Rahmen des TA-Programms des Schweizerischen Wissenschafts- und Technologierates (SWTR) durchgeführt wurden.

Mit TA (Technology Assessment / Technologiefolgen-Abschätzung) werden dabei Projekte bezeichnet, welche zum Ziel haben, die gesellschaftlichen Auswirkungen neuer Technologien möglichst umfassend zu untersuchen. Es geht darum, die allfälligen positiven und negativen Einflüsse der Technologie auf soziale, politische, wirtschaftliche und ökologische Systeme und Abläufe abzuschätzen.

Nach einer Pilotphase von 4 Jahren haben der Bundesrat und das Parlament den SWTR beauftragt, die TA-Aktivitäten für die Periode 1996-1999 weiterzuführen.

Um diese Aufgabe zu erfüllen, wurde vom SWTR ein TA-Leitungsausschuss aus Fachleuten von Wissenschaft, Industrie, Politik und NGO's (Nichtstaatliche Organisationen) eingesetzt, welcher die massgeblichen Themen und Fragen definiert, die es im TA-Programm zu behandeln gilt.

Ende 1999 wurde vom Parlament beschlossen, die Technologiefolgen-Abschätzung zu institutionalisieren. Dies ist im Bundesgesetz über die Forschung vom 8. Oktober 1999 festgehalten.

Die materielle Verantwortung für den Bericht liegt bei der Autorin:

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Der ausführliche Bericht "Computerbasierte Patientendossiers - Chancen und Risiken" kann bezogen werden bei der nebenstehenden Adresse.

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Cette série des publications TA contient les résultats des projets menés dans le cadre du programme TA du Conseil suisse de la science et de la technologie (CSST).

Sous la dénomination TA (Technology Assessment / évaluation des choix technologiques), on comprend les projets visant à cerner, de la manière la plus approfondie possible, les effets des nouvelles technologies sur la société. Il s'agit là des influences potentielles, aussi bien positives que négatives, que la technologie peut avoir sur des procédures et des systèmes sociaux, politiques, économiques et écologiques.

Après une phase-pilote de 4 années, le Conseil fédéral et le Parlement ont chargé le CSST de poursuivre les activités du programme TA pour la période 1996-1999.

Pour répondre à cette demande, le CSST a nommé un Comité Directeur composé de scientifiques, de spécialistes des domaines industriel et politique ainsi que des représentants des organisations non gouvernementales (ONG).

Fin 1999, le Parlement a décidé d'institutionnaliser les activités du Technology Assessment. Cette décision est inscrite dans la loi fédérale sur la recherche du 8 octobre 1999.

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Le rapport complet "Computerbasierte Patientendossiers - Chancen und Risiken" est disponible à l'adresse suivante:

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AN ELECTRONIC PICTURE OF THE PATIENT

A REALITY IN THE NEAR FUTURE?

1

Computer-based patient records are electronically managed health records. In Switzerland they are already being used in certain cases because they are easier to manage than the often bulky files on paper, more easily available and easier to access for analyses, be it for scientific purposes, preventive medicine programmes or for the insurance companies. Furthermore, computer-based patient records mean that further uses of telemedicine can be envisaged. Despite initial problems when the system was introduced, a broad use, standardisation and networking of patients' records on computer is now feasible. Notwithstanding these advantages, however, potential risks, principally from the point of view of data protection and IT security, must also be considered when the system is introduced.

From a hand-written to a computer-based patient record

Doctors are obliged to note the details of all stages of treatment given in the patient's medical record. The same applies to dentists and other medical people such as psychotherapists, physiotherapists, etc. The patient's medical record is a detailed description and a report of the treatment given and serves at the same time as a tool. It contains information about diagnoses and treatment, X-rays, the results of laboratory analyses, etc. In addition, the therapy agreed upon as well as explanations given to the patient by the doctor are documented. The patient's medical record is part of his or her file.

Until now patient records have been kept mainly in written form on paper. In the near future we shall see computer-based patient records that include everything from the administrative details – name, date of birth, insurance number, etc. – to the medical history of the patient. Computer-based patient records are often referred to as digital or electronic health records. The term "computer-based patient record" also implies the functional changes due to the increasing use of computers.

The patient's file not only contains information about him or her but also, in a way, represents a model of the patient, since a doctor will base his decisions not only on his consultation with the patient but also on the information provided in the file. This procedure is in fact underlined by the introduction of electronic health records, since they contain more information compared to printed files, they are largely standardised and are more readily evaluated.

Computer-based patient records are classified according to the treatment received by the patient: each treatment is documented by the corresponding examinations and a report on the findings. There already exist multimedia documents which include, apart from text, pictorial information such as X-rays or computer tomograms. So far, however, many systems are limited to text only.

Pioneers in the introduction of computer-based patient records

We are still far from a full computerisation of our health records. There are only few computer-based patient records in Swiss hospitals and abroad, and they are often kept alongside written records.

Examples within Switzerland

The University Hospital in Geneva has so far set up over a million computer-based patient records but still keeps conventional written records which doctors carry with them on their rounds, for example. The canton of Vaud is planning to link up its hospitals to a network through which information on patients can be exchanged between different hospitals, while all the hospitals in the canton of Neuchâtel have been linked via Intranet since 1997 and can thus exchange electronic information on patients.

The computerisation of patients' files has various aims. While most hospitals are trying to improve the processing and communication of information within their walls, some are already aiming to establish comprehensive networking, i.e. a system which includes several health facilities. In addition, computer-based patient records can be used with

other newly developing facilities such as telemedicine.

2

KNOW-HOW – ABILITY – FEASIBILITY? ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Improvements in medical care

In future, computer-based patient records will generally contain more data and information than the traditional written files. Doctors and nurses will thus be able to gain a more detailed but naturally in many ways still a limited picture of the patient. At the same time computer-based systems will help to master the constantly growing scope of medical knowledge. With computer-based patient records it is already possible today, for example, to acquire additional information concerning results of laboratory tests for a certain patient. The most significant advantage, however, is the speed at which information is available and can be evaluated and passed on. This will become important in emer-

gency cases, for example, where it is essential to treat the patient quickly.

In comparison with written records, computer-based patient records offer important advantages regarding evaluation, quality control and statistical analysis. It is often extremely difficult to make an efficient analysis on the basis of written records. This will change once computer-based patient records are in general use; since different elements of the patient's medical record will no longer be kept in separate places but will be kept together in one single file, considerable progress in research – for example in epidemiology – can be expected. By evaluating anonymous patient data it will be possible to decide at an early stage, when a preventive programme should be introduced. Or until

now unrecognised symptoms of a later illness will be identified, which will lead to rapid therapeutic action. Furthermore, it will be possible to continually assess the success of preventive programmes, an important factor for health insurance companies among others, which will then be able to offer more specifically targeted health-care programmes than has been the case so far.

Design new developments to avoid risks

Among those employed in the health sector in particular computer-based patient records are not always receiving a positive welcome. During the introductory phase entering patients' data and scanning images has led in many cases to an increase in the work load. There have also been complaints about the checking facilities involved in computer-based patient records, which are generally putting more pressure on performance for those working in the health sector. In addition, doctors fear that their role as the patient's representative and direct contact in the hospital may well change in that, in the future, they may become merely a provider of specialised services. The doctor's "craft" is being brought into question by the increase in supporting technical functions and transparency. Furthermore, what has been up until now a close relationship between the patient and the doctor is likely to become more distant if a greater number of doctors are involved in consultation and treatment of one patient.

It can also be said, however, that the introduction of computer-based patient records will lead to a more structured and standardised contact between patients and doctors, which may influence the patients' confidence in the doctors and the quality of the medical treatment they receive. For many patients confidence in a doctor and understanding of the situation are only established over a period of time. If the doctor gives his or her diagnosis too early in the consultation, important information and the patient's wishes may not be mentioned and the main problem may not be addressed at all, especially if this involves statements which are per-

What is telemedicine?

Computer-based patient records are part of a rapid and complex development in the direction of medical services and activities which are based on modern information and communication methods. Such applications are generally referred to as "telemedicine". Telemedicine includes telepathology, whereby images of organic-anatomical changes – often microscopic images of tissue samples – can be transmitted electronically. Telemedicine also comprises remote medical treatment, for example telesurgery, or telemonitoring, which is the observation of a patient at home.

Computer-based patient records are an important prerequisite for other applications of telemedicine. For example providing remote medical therapy would not be possible unless information concerning the patient is available electronically to all those involved.

sonally difficult for the patient. If this problem is taken into account, virtual records can improve the initial situation for a consultation with a doctor since they contain more information more easily ingestible. A patient consultation should therefore be quite open at first, and the computer-based patient record should only be called up after a sufficiently long introductory phase.

At present, we do not know whether and in what way the increased use of computer-based patient records will affect the cost of health care. It is true, that it could well prove economical in the long term, e.g. by avoiding the duplication of examinations. Initially, however, the introduction of computer-based patient records will mean considerable investment and subsequent expenditure. A positive effect on the cost of the health service could be achieved through improved transparency, for example, as well as the resulting increase in competition between the different elements in the health sector, time saved through automation of routine tasks

and the simplification of administrative and accounting procedures. On the other hand, a negative aspect is that computer-based patient records can only be used to a limited extent in connection with existing, well de-

veloped systems. Several university hospitals have therefore got together to work out a common solution for a computer-based patient record. The results of their deliberations should provide a model which can also be used by other hospitals.

3

DATA ABUSE AND WHAT CAN BE DONE TO PREVENT IT

It is a more complex matter to protect electronic information on patients than written data. For this reason it is important to take the necessary precautions with regard to security before computer-based patient records are introduced.

People who are ill want first and foremost to be cured, which is why they seek medical help. How their files are handled is not their main concern at that moment. The amount of interest patients are showing in their medical records is growing, though, and awareness of the question of data protection has increased considerably over the past few years.

The patient decides about his or her data

Patients are the mandators of their medical treatment. This means that they have the right to consult their medical history, in particular the diagnoses made so far, so that they can accept or refuse any treatment proposed.

At present there is widespread agreement that access to data concerning any patient, as well as additions or changes to those data, must be authorised by the patient in question. Without the patient's approval, important data may not be erased or changed. In addition, patients should play an active role in deciding which data may be made accessi-

ble to third parties and which data are to be kept confidential.

With the development of computer-based patient records to provide a detailed life-long medical history of each patient, the patient's interest in the stored data will increase. Under certain circumstances it will be possible for patients to consult their own medical records through their own PC. The difficulty to interpret the information in a patient's record has already arisen. Any patient who wishes to consult his or her medical record therefore generally does so with the help of a medically trained person who provides explanations, translates the contents of the file into everyday terms and tries to prevent misunderstandings arising – in psychiatry, for example, where the same expression often means something quite different in laymen's or specialists' language.

In future, when medical records for the patients in question are made available to them, the role of the medical adviser will be partly taken over by an electronic understanding aid function, the so-called patient information systems. In order to ensure that such systems are suitable and are not biased towards certain interests, such as the health insuran-

ce or pharmaceutical companies, they should be subject to quality assurance criteria. Information systems may help patients to be more critical of medical treatment, to take the relevant decisions and to play a more active role in remaining healthy or regaining their health. They thus strengthen the patient's responsibility and ability to make an informed decision.

At the same time, however, fears have been voiced that the use of information systems – for example through preprogrammed decision-making aids – could have a negative effect on the decisions taken by doctors which involve a certain degree of responsibility and are focused on the individual patient. The important thing is that in future human decisions in the health sector remain a priority. Increasing technology and specialisation and regulated routine procedures must not lead to a weakening of the personal relationship between the patient and his or her doctor nor a responsible decision taken by health-care specialists losing its importance.

Security is a priority

There is always the risk with medical records that important data concerning the patient are no longer accessible or are changed, for example owing to technical failure, or that access is gained to confidential information by unauthorised people. Such risks increase with computer-based patient records mainly because the more complex the system the greater the danger of authorised access being blocked or technical faults remaining undiscovered, as well as the fact that it is possible to gain unauthorised access to a greater volume of data.

These risks must therefore be eliminated early on by implementing suitable technical and organisational measures. A few important examples of such measures are given below.

- Anyone wishing to consult data on a patient must identify himself or herself, for example through a password. Access is possible only by authorised people and

By the patient information systems patients can inform themselves more easily and therefore take more responsibility concerning their medical treatment.

(Picture: German ministry for education and research)

with the agreement of the patient in question.

- Within a hospital or any other health-care institution different levels of access are authorised. Nurses may only consult data which directly involves their own work, for example.
- Any addition or alteration of data must bear a digital signature.
- The identity of any person who consults patient data is recorded and this information is kept over a certain period of time. Any abuse of the system can thus be easily traced.
- The system allows patient data to be transmitted or stored on a mobile medium only in a coded form.
- After a given period of time certain data must be erased or may not be made available to third parties at all.

Today little attention is often paid to the protection of patient data. Awareness of this issue needs to be generally promoted in the health sector. People who use computer-based patient records should be made aware of the risks and encouraged to handle patient data in a responsible way.

Who owns the data?

Basically patients' records are the property of the medical institution which has drawn them up. Under the strict terms of the law property rights cover only the material comprising the medium such as paper, floppy disks or personal computers. Concerning the contents of a patient's record, personal rights are more important to the patient than property rights. The laws of the canton of Geneva specifically state that patient data drawn up by a health-care institution are the property of the patient.

From the point of view of both the patient and the user it should not be made too difficult and time-consuming to use computer-based patient records, otherwise there is the danger that patients will be divided in two groups – either those who can take advantage of the new possibilities of access and availability, or those who are totally overw-

handed by the security procedures. Acceptance among medical staff is generally reduced by complicated security procedures. Experience has shown that problems with data protection arise less frequently in technologically secured sectors than when such measures are not applied.

Precise regulations in the legislation

Patient records require a high degree of data protection. As more and more systems of virtual life-long records are set up such requirements will increase and under certain circumstances they will have to be subject to international regulation. We have not got that far yet, however. At present federal and

PATIENT CARD OR VIRTUAL FILE?

There are various storage media and models available for use with computer-based patient records. We cannot yet say what the file of the future will look like. There will probably be increasing networking between health-care institutions, which will require a higher level of coordination and standardisation.

cantonal legislation includes various, partly overlapping regulations relating to data protection in the medical sector. Secure handling of the data contained in computer-based patient records has not yet been comprehensively and specifically regulated; there are no practical rules specifically aimed at computer-based patient records which can be applied to ensure effective prevention of data abuse.

There are several possible ways in which patient data could be stored. Patient cards on which data is stored, like a credit card, would be the most convenient for the patient. The-

re is a considerable risk, however, that such a card would not be found just when it is needed in an emergency. Furthermore, such cards can easily be lost and under certain circumstances sensitive data could then be accessed by unauthorised parties.

There would be no risk of loss in the use of implanted microchips containing medical information about the patient, but such a system is hardly likely to be generally accepted. The use of microchips is feasible perhaps with regard to a small group of high-

risk patients where information essential to survival needs to be available at all times.

The most probable development in the future is therefore virtual, life-long patient records. With this system data concerning patients is stored at various points in doctors' surgeries, hospitals, etc. where the patient is receiving treatment at the time. But with the patient's agreement, authorised institutions can consult the whole file at any time and when required it would be possible to make evaluations which involve a longer

period of time and several different health-care institutions. Initial efforts are being made in Switzerland at the moment to link up medical institutions in different cantons, but the federal structure of the country's health system is not making the task an easy one.

It would be feasible in the future, for example, for tissue samples taken from a patient in the Cantonal Hospital in Baden to be analysed by a specialist in the University Hospital in Geneva and that a medical robot which carries out part of a microsurgical operation

With the new computer-based patient records (example of the Höhenklinik Wald) patients data can be administrated centrally and stored for a lifetime.

COORDINATION AND SPECIFIC DETAILS – PROSPECTS FOR THE FUTURE

Like other technical innovations, computer-based patient records present both advantages and dangers. Until now they have been developed largely autonomously, based on individual initiative. In the future it will be necessary to have increased planning and coordination in this field. Professional people from various disciplines, but also representatives of those directly involved, i.e. patients' organisations, will need to be included in the design and introduction of computer-based patient records systems.

is programmed by a team of experts in Lyon. In fact the possibility of transmitting data electronically as well as setting up a "virtual hospital" is getting closer and closer: in days to come different medical institutions could treat a patient jointly, even across national borders. It is also imaginable that other medical and social services apart from hospitals – for example home-help for the bed-ridden or handicapped and physiotherapy – would be included in such health-care networks. The introduction of computer-based patient records is part of the future development of the health-care sector, medicine and medical information technology. There will be conflicts of interests when written medical records are replaced by computer-based patient records. It will be necessary, for example:

- to ensure greater efficiency in medical treatment, but not at the patient's expense,
- to have more information which is generally accessible, e.g. for epidemiological purposes, without compromising data protection,
- to ensure more transparency in health-care procedures without excessive control of those directly involved,
- to improve quality assurance without limiting the scope of activity of medical staff, and
- to guarantee competitiveness for small and medium-sized manufacturers of medical

software while ensuring reliable, internationally compatible solutions.

Thus there is a need for action in many areas. The existing regulations governing data protection and security are very general with regard to computer-based patient records. It would therefore be useful to have, among other things, guidelines for handling personal data in the medical sector, help with regard to the application of electronic systems and recommendations for those responsible in the health-care sector.

Regulations and recommendations reflect the state of public discussion. Up until now, handling patients' data has hardly been a public issue. Meetings and media contributions should be used to encourage public debate on this topic.

In future users and manufacturers of computer-based patient records systems will be required to agree on a coordinated procedure in order to avoid duplication and problems of compatibility. It would be advisable to include experts from quite different fields, such as data protection and health psychology, in designing and introducing computer-based patient record systems. In addition, all those directly affected should have a say in design and introduction procedures. This would include in particular those who use computer-based patient records as well as representatives of patients' organisations.

The essential issues concerning further development of computer-based patient records include data security, data protection